

Farmer's Yards: Supporting Farm Succession Through Social Connection in Later Life

For many older farmers, the prospect of stepping back from farming represents one of the most significant transitions they will face in later life. Farming is not simply an occupation but a lifelong identity deeply connected to family, community and place. Yet farm succession is often approached primarily through legal, financial and taxation considerations, while the emotional and social dimensions of the transition process receive far less attention. Across Ireland and internationally, ageing farming populations, declining numbers of young entrants and growing concerns around farmer wellbeing have intensified discussions about how succession is supported. This research explores how social connection, peer support and World Health Organization (WHO) age-friendly approaches can support older farmers in navigating succession and retirement while maintaining purpose, dignity, wellbeing and meaningful engagement within their farming communities.

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Research Overview

Published in the Journal of Agromedicine in 2024, this research examines the development, implementation and early lessons emerging from Farmer's Yards, an innovative social initiative designed to support older farmers through the emotional and practical challenges associated with succession and retirement. The initiative was informed by findings from the Irish component of the International FARMTRANSFERS Survey, a global study involving almost 18,000 farmers across 13 countries and eight U.S. states, which explored older farmers' attitudes, intentions and experiences relating to succession and retirement. Initially piloted at Mountbellew Livestock Mart, Co. Galway in 2023, the initiative created safe and familiar spaces where farmers could discuss succession, wellbeing, ageing and future planning with their peers. The pilot engaged more than 300 participants over a six-week period and generated strong interest from farmers and service providers, highlighting a previously unmet need for social and emotional support alongside traditional succession planning services. Drawing on participant feedback, stakeholder engagement and implementation experience, the research explores how age-friendly approaches can complement existing wellbeing and succession supports and strengthen outcomes for older farmers and their communities.

Key Insights / Findings

The Farmer's Yards pilot revealed strong demand for opportunities where older farmers could openly discuss concerns relating to ageing, retirement, identity, loneliness and the future of their farms. The initiative demonstrated that trusted peer-to-peer environments can encourage earlier and more meaningful conversations around succession, helping to reduce uncertainty and stigma associated with stepping back from farming. Participants valued having a familiar, dedicated space to share experiences and learn from others facing similar transitions. The evidence suggests that social connection and emotional wellbeing are important, yet often overlooked, components of successful succession planning. More broadly, it highlights the importance of creating opportunities for dialogue, trust and peer support throughout the transition process. Collectively, the lessons learned reinforce the need for more holistic approaches that recognise both the human and operational dimensions of intergenerational farm transfer.

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Further Reading:

Conway, S. F., Farrell, M.,
McDonagh, J. and Nolan, N.
(2024) Creating an Age-Friendly
Environment in Farming – The
Farmer’s Yards Approach, *Journal
of Agromedicine*, 29(4), 717–724.
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AgriFood & AgriTech

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SDG 3: Good Health & Well-Being

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Why it Matters

With ageing farming populations presenting challenges across the world, there is growing interest in approaches that support older farmers beyond traditional advisory, legal and financial services. Farmer’s Yards demonstrates how relatively simple, community-based interventions can create meaningful opportunities for engagement, support and knowledge exchange. The pilot highlighted the value of delivering support within familiar and trusted community settings, helping to encourage participation and open discussion. By placing social inclusion and peer support at the centre of succession discussions, the initiative complements existing advisory services while helping farmers address issues that are often difficult to discuss in formal settings. It also challenges assumptions that retirement from farming necessarily means withdrawal from farming life, instead emphasising continued contribution, mentorship and community engagement. The model aligns with broader policy objectives relating to generational renewal, healthy ageing, rural wellbeing and sustainable farming communities, demonstrating how research-informed social innovation can support older farmers through periods of transition and change in later life.

What’s Next?

Following its successful pilot in Ireland, Farmer’s Yards was adapted and rolled out in the state of Pennsylvania, U.S.A. in January 2025 by Pennsylvania Farm Link (PFL), supported by funding from the USDA National Institute of Food and Agriculture and the Northeast Extension Risk Management Education Centre. The successful transfer of the model to a very different agricultural context demonstrates its wider relevance and scalability. Interest in the approach is also growing nationally, including through engagement with Age Friendly Ireland following a feature on RTÉ Radio 1 in February 2026 and subsequent calls in Dáil Éireann for its expansion in May 2026. Internationally, the initiative was showcased at the International Farm Transition Network (IFTN) Annual Conference in Gettysburg, Pennsylvania, in June 2026, bringing the concept to a global audience of researchers, educators and practitioners working on farm succession. Future work will continue to explore how age-friendly and community-based approaches can support older farmers during succession and retirement transitions. The lessons learned offer valuable insights for policymakers, advisory services and rural development organisations seeking to support farming communities through demographic change, healthy ageing and generational renewal.

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